

Integrating Business Intelligence and Small and Medium Enterprises for Shifting Africa from Consumption to a Production and Industrialised Economy

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Abstract—An excessive reliance on consumption and importation has long characterised the economic environment in Africa, impeding Africa's potential to establish a self-sufficient and industrialised economy. Small and medium-sized businesses (SMEs) are vital actors in Africa's development because they play a critical role in fostering economic growth and the creation of jobs. In order to empower SMEs and speed up the transition to a production- and industrialized-based economy, this study examines the possibilities of business intelligence (BI) tools and tactics. This study explores the difficulties SMEs in Africa currently face, such as restricted access to financing, inadequate infrastructure, and a lack of technological improvements. These barriers make it difficult for them to compete on a global scale and help sustain a consumption-based economy. These problems may be solved by the broad idea of business intelligence. SMEs can acquire a competitive advantage and promote sustainable economic growth by utilising the potential of data analytics, predictive modelling, and strategic decision-making. This study examines several BI tools and approaches, including data mining, predictive analytics, and data visualisation, and emphasises how they may be used to improve the productivity, effectiveness, and profitability of SMEs. The study also looks at examples of successful BI-driven economic transformation in other locations through case studies. These case studies offer useful information about the possible effects of BI adoption in the African setting and provide a road map for decision-makers, business owners, and other interested parties seeking to hasten the transition to a production- and industrialized-based economy.

Index Terms—Business Intelligence, SMEs, consumption, production, Industrialised-based economy

I. INTRODUCTION

The importance of SMEs and business intelligence in Africa's shift from a consumption-based economy to a production- and industrialized-based economy is examined in this study. It draws attention to the significance of SMEs in Africa, which make a substantial contribution to job creation, poverty alleviation, and general economic progress (Adams et al., 2023). However, financial resources, technological infrastructure, and data access are frequently scarce for SMEs

(Agbajor & Mewomo, 2022). The study offers a thorough review of business information and its importance for SMEs, discusses methods for overcoming these difficulties, and offers helpful advice. The study also explores the value of creating a data-driven culture and offers solutions for dealing with change resistance. It also emphasises the necessity of improved government policies and support for business intelligence deployment in SMEs (Ashiru et al., 2022). It also emphasises how crucial training and capacity-building initiatives are to enabling SMEs to use business intelligence tools and methodologies. SMEs are crucial to Africa's economy because they provide a lot of jobs, fight poverty, and promote economic progress (Antoniadis et al., 2015). However, companies encounter a number of difficulties, including restricted access to financing, poor infrastructure, a shortage of competent labour, and problems with market access (Gaglio et al., 2022). Data-driven decision-making has become increasingly important for organisations of all kinds in the quickly changing business world of today (Brodny, 2022). SMEs may effectively utilise their data assets, optimise operations, spot market trends, and make wise strategic decisions by implementing business intelligence (Gonzalez-tamayo et al., 2023; Kubina et al., 2015). SMEs may gain a competitive edge, boost efficiency, raise customer happiness, and promote sustainable growth by utilising the potential of BI.

The purpose of this study is to shed light on the significance of SMEs and business intelligence in Africa's economic development. It also explore how the adoption of business intelligence can empower SMEs to transition from a consumption-based economy to a production-based and industrialised economy. By achieving this transition, African countries can enhance their competitiveness, reduce dependency on imports, and foster sustainable economic growth. The specific objectives are as follows:

- To provide a comprehensive overview of the current state of BI and SMEs' integration and focus in Africa, including their contributions, challenges, and potential for growth.

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Digital Object Identifier: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10056827>

- To highlight the benefits and opportunities that can arise from implementing business intelligence in African SMEs.
- To identify effective business intelligence tools, techniques, and strategies that can be adopted by SMEs in Africa.
- To analyse proposed case studies of African SMEs that have implemented business intelligence and achieved significant growth.
- To address the challenges and barriers faced by African SMEs in adopting and implementing business intelligence and propose strategies to overcome them.

By addressing these objectives, the study contributes to the existing knowledge base and provide practical insights that can facilitate the sustainable growth and development of SMEs in Africa, ultimately driving economic transformation and prosperity.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW AND RELATED WORKS

The term "business intelligence" describes the procedure of gathering, analysing, and deciphering enormous amounts of data in order to gain knowledge and make wise business decisions (Antoniadis et al., 2015; Cavazza et al., 2023; Helo & Hao, 2022). It entails utilising methods, tools, and technology to turn unstructured data into knowledge that can be used for competitive advantage, operational effectiveness, and strategic planning (Hajipour et al., 2023). For a number of reasons, SMEs are essential to fostering economic development and prosperity in Africa. Job creation: SMEs account for a sizable share of the labour market, including women and young people (Kubina et al., 2015). SMEs contribute to poverty alleviation, social stability, and inclusive growth by creating employment possibilities (Kudama et al., 2021). Entrepreneurship and innovation: SMEs frequently serve as the breeding grounds for these two phenomena, fostering technological improvements, product diversification, and market competitiveness (Potgieter et al., 2013). Its adaptability and readiness to take chances encourage creativity and fuel economic dynamism. Value addition and industrialization: SMEs have the power to increase the value of raw materials, encourage domestic processing, and support the industrialization of African economies.

Furthermore, SMEs can improve competitiveness, lessen its reliance on imports, and promote sustainable economic growth by rising up the value chain. Regional commerce and integration: SMEs in Africa have the power to promote regional trade and integration. SMEs can support cross-border commerce, improve market access, and advance economic cooperation among African nations (Siah et al., 2016). Resilience and inclusivity: SMEs show resilience in unpredictable economic times and give marginalised groups, like women and youth, a chance to engage in economic activity (Moyo & Loock, 2021). Its inclusiveness fosters sustainable growth, enhances social cohesion, and lowers inequality (Sharma et al., 2022). For policymakers, researchers, and stakeholders to develop targeted interventions, supportive policies, and initiatives that can unlock the potential of SMEs and propel sustainable economic growth in Africa, it is essential to understand the

Fig. 1. PRISMA Sample flowchart of the study.

African SME landscape and the challenges faced by these businesses (Manning et al., 2022; Mezgebe et al., 2023).

III. METHODOLOGY

The study approach utilised to investigate how business intelligence and small and medium-sized enterprises could be used to shift Africa's economy from one of consumption to one of production and industrialization. To learn more about the current processes, the qualitative component involves reviewing previously published books, academic research, and case studies ranging from 2015 to 2023. To get qualitative data, a variety of procedures have been utilized such as PRISMA sample selection flowchart (see Figure 1). Moreover, Boolean search technique was employed as (business intelligence AND (small and medium enterprises)); and (African consumption economy OR (African production economy AND (Africa industrialised economy))); and finally where title, abstract, and content criteria is carefully observed. Gaining a more thorough understanding of the topic can also benefit from a careful review 35 of the most recent academic research, scholarly writings, and information from trustworthy sources as shown in Figure 1. The literature was gathered from Google Scholar, Science Direct, Emerald Insight, Research Gate, and Academia to conduct a study on turning African consumption into production using a qualitative methodology (see Figure 2). From written sources for qualitative data, repeating themes, patterns, and significant ideas can be extracted using a thematic analysis technique. The influence may be seen in the data with the help of these techniques and the ICT resources that are available. By shifting Africa's economy from one of consumption to one of production and industrialization, we can better understand the integration of business intelligence and small and medium enterprises. To evaluate statistical patterns and trends related to Africa's economy's shift from one of consumption to one of production. The impact of BI and SMEs on this transformation goal is examined in this paper.

Fig. 2. Sample of the study based on research databases.

IV. DISCUSSION AND FINDINGS

Comprehensive overview of the current state of BI and SMEs' integration techniques and focus in Africa, including their contributions, challenges, and potential for growth.

SMEs are the foundation of the African economy and are essential to job creation, poverty alleviation, and general economic growth. SME definitions in Africa are based on factors including assets, turnover, and personnel count (Zide & Jokonya, 2022). These businesses range in size from micro-enterprises with a tiny staff to small and medium-sized ones with a larger workforce and a greater turnover rate. A wide range of industries, including manufacturing, services, technology products and services, few technology firms, and agriculture, make up the African SME scene (Llave & Llave, 2017). These businesses represent a sizeable portion of economic activity and make a considerable contribution to the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) of African nations (Zahoor et al., 2023). It promote inclusive growth and economic dynamism by creating possibilities for entrepreneurship, innovation, and market competition.

Despite being significant, SMEs in Africa face various obstacles that prevent them from expanding and remaining viable. These difficulties include: (i) Limited access to finance: SMEs frequently struggle to find affordable funding since financial institutions view them as high-risk borrowers. Its capacity to invest in technology, grow business, and look into new market opportunities is constrained by their limited access to money (Sharma et al., 2022). (ii) Poor infrastructure: Small and medium-sized businesses face difficult obstacles as a result of poor transportation, unpredictable electricity, and restricted access to broadband internet. These infrastructure weaknesses raise operating costs, hinder productivity, and restrict SMEs' capacity to successfully compete (Habibzadeh et al., 2020). (iii) Lack of trained labour: Due to competition from larger businesses and a lack of funding for training and development, SMEs frequently struggle to recruit and retain competent workers. Productivity, creativity, and SMEs' capac-

ity to adopt new technologies are all hindered by the labour crisis (H. Li, 2021). (iv) Limited market access: Due to issues including trade regulations, a lack of market information, and challenges in adhering to quality standards and certifications, SMEs encounter barriers when trying to enter domestic and international markets (Adam et al., 2020). The opportunity for growth is constrained, and there are fewer prospects for expansion. (v) Inadequate access to specific business support services, such as mentoring, advisory services, and training programmes, is a common problem for SMEs (Bergener et al., 2019). It unable to effectively build business plans, enhance operations, or overcome obstacles in the absence of such support services.

- Benefits and opportunities that can arise from implementing business intelligence in African SMEs. Data integration, data warehousing, data mining, reporting, and data visualisation are all included in the idea of business intelligence. It makes it possible for SMEs to collect information from many sources, analyse it, and derive useful insights that can direct their decision-making procedures (Benzidia & Metz, 2020; Kubina et al., 2015). Many advantages can result from SMEs implementing a business intelligence system, these potency's include: Making decisions based on data: BI enables SMEs to take well-informed decisions based on precise and current information (Llave & Llave, 2017). Businesses can find patterns, trends, and correlations by analysing data from a variety of sources. These findings can then be used to inform risk management, resource allocation, and strategic planning. Increased operational effectiveness: By discovering bottlenecks, inefficiencies, and potential areas for improvement, BI helps SMEs streamline their operations. Key performance indicator (KPI) data analysis enables firms to streamline operations, cut costs, and boost productivity. Improved customer insights: BI enables SMEs to learn more about the preferences, actions, and requirements of their clients (Helo & Hao, 2022; Toorajipour et al., 2021). Businesses may personalise their marketing campaigns, raise customer satisfaction, and foster client loyalty by analysing customer data (Helo & Hao, 2022). Competitive advantage: By staying on top of market trends, keeping tabs on rivals' movements, and seeing new opportunities, BI helps SMEs acquire a competitive edge (Dash et al., 2019; Naz et al., 2022; Nikoloski, 2014). Businesses may take proactive actions, respond rapidly to market developments, and set themselves apart from rivals by utilising data insights (Kubina et al., 2015). Forecasting and risk management: By delivering real-time data and predictive analytics, BI aids SMEs in identifying and reducing risks (Lin et al., 2022; Richter et al., 2022). Businesses may identify possible problems, foresee market changes, and take proactive action to reduce risks and maximise possibilities by keeping an eye on key data.
- Effective business intelligence tools, techniques, and strategies that can be adopted by SMEs in Africa. A holistic instrument that assists SMEs in gathering, analysing,

TABLE I
CURRENT STATE OF BI AND SMEs INTEGRATION TECHNIQUES, AND FOCUS

Integration Technique and Source	Integration Focus	Journal Publisher
Internationalizing African SMEs towards a new agenda. (Zahoor et al., 2023)	African SMEs	Journal of Business Research
Competence and enterprise of management as drivers. (Adams et al., 2023)	Medium-sized emerging market multinationals from Africa	Journal of Business Research
Industry 4.0. (Peter et al., 2023)	Sub-Saharan African SME manufacturing sector	Procedia Computer Science
Factors influencing small and medium size enterprises development and digital maturity. (Gonzalez-tamayo et al., 2023)	Latin America	Journal of Open Innovation: Technology, Market, and Complexity
A value-oriented Artificial Intelligence-as-a-Service business plan. (Hajipour et al., 2023)	Using integrated tools and services	Decision Analytics Journal
Intelligent manufacturing eco-system A post COVID-19 recovery and growth opportunity for manufacturing industry in Sub-Saharan countries. (Mezgebe et al., 2023)	Sub-Saharan countries	Scientific African
Factors affecting the adoption of Data Management as a Service (DMaaS) in Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs). (Zide Jokonya, 2022)	Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs)	Procedia Computer Science
The Level of Digitization of Small, Medium and Large Enterprises and Its Relationship with Economic Parameters. (Brodny, 2022)	Central and Eastern European Countries	Journal of Open Innovation: Technology, Market, and Complexity
Is a digital transformation framework enough for manufacturing smart products? (Sharma et al., 2022)	The case of Small and Medium Enterprises	Procedia Manufacturing
Green building research in South Africa: A scoping review and future roadmaps. (Agbajor Mewomo, 2022)	South Africa	Energy and Built Environment
Digital transformation on innovation and productivity. (Gaglio et al., 2022)	South African Manufacturing Micro and Small Enterprises	Technological Forecasting and Social Change
Relational governance mechanisms for dynamic capabilities. (Ashiru et al., 2022)	Nigerian SMEs during Covid-19	Industrial Marketing Management
Will digital solution transform Sub-Sahara African agriculture? (Kudama et al., 2021)	Sub-Sahara African Agriculture	Artificial Intelligence in Agriculture
Conceptualising a Cloud Business Intelligence Security Evaluation Framework. (Moyo Look, 2021)	for Small and Medium Enterprises in Small Towns of the Limpopo Province, South Africa	Information
An innovative business model. (Vanadzina et al., 2019)	For rural sub-Saharan Africa electrification	Energy Procedi
Business Intelligence and Analytics in Small and Medium-sized Enterprises. (Llave Llave, 2017)	Small and Medium-sized Enterprises	Procedia Computer Science
Assessing the Supply Chain Intelligence Practices of Small Medium Enterprises in Malaysia. (Siah et al., 2016)	Malaysian SMEs	Procedia Economics and Finance
Possibility of improving efficiency within business intelligence systems in companies. (Kubina et al., 2015)	Companies	Procedia Economics and Finance
Business Intelligence during times of crisis. (Antoniadis et al., 2015)	Adoption and usage of ERP systems by SMEs	Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences
An innovative marketing information system. (Potgieter et al., 2013)	Management tool for South African tour operators	Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences

and making choices is a business intelligence system. Data integration, data warehousing, data mining, reporting and dashboards, data visualisation, and predictive analytics are some of its essential elements (Benzidia & Metz, 2020). In order to ensure that all relevant data is integrated and readily available for analysis, data integration entails collecting data from many sources, including internal databases, external systems, and third-party sources. An organised environment for effective data retrieval and analysis is provided by data warehousing, which stores and organises data in a central repository. Data mining is the process of exploring and identifying patterns, correlations, and trends within data using sophisticated statistical techniques and algorithms (Dumitrascu et al., 2020; Li, 2022). This procedure aids SMEs in gaining insightful information and making data-driven choices. Reporting and dashboards give data visual representations, enabling

SMEs to measure performance, monitor KPIs, and get instant insights (Potgieter et al., 2013). Users can generate personalised reports, interactive dashboards, and visualisations using these tools for efficient data exchange. Moreover, charts, graphs, and maps are examples of data visualisation strategies that assist SMEs in comprehending large data sets and effectively communicating findings. Predictive analytics helps SMEs foresee customer behaviour, market demand, and company hazards so they can take proactive action (Kersten et al., 2019). It does this by using historical data and statistical models to estimate future outcomes and trends. For SMEs to acquire and transform unstructured data into actionable insights, efficient data gathering and analysis methodologies are essential. Data extraction, data cleaning, data integration, data exploration, data modelling, and reports are examples of techniques. While dashboards offer a consolidated

view of key performance indicators (KPIs) and metrics, charts and graphs provide a visual representation of data and show patterns or similarities (Dumitrascu et al., 2020). Infographics communicate data in a visually appealing way by fusing textual and visual elements (Dumitrascu et al., 2020; Peter et al., 2023). SMEs can predict future events and trends based on historical data thanks to forecasting and predictive analytics approaches. Regression analysis, time series analysis, machine learning algorithms, simulation, and scenario analysis are methods frequently used in predictive analytics. These tools and methods for business intelligence can help SMEs make better decisions, obtain important insights from their data, and expand their businesses. These methods and technologies help SMEs stay competitive in a market that is changing quickly while also empowering them to take proactive, data-driven actions.

V. ANALYSIS OF PROPOSED CASE STUDIES

In this section we are analyzing proposed case studies of African SMEs that have implemented business intelligence and achieved significant growth.

A. Case study 1: How Company X utilized BI to increase productivity and profitability

In this case study, we examine the effective application of business intelligence (BI) tools and practises by Company X, an African SME, to increase productivity and profitability. Company X understood the need to enhance decision-making procedures and get more comprehension of its business operations. It put into place an extensive BI system with capabilities for data gathering, processing, visualisation, and reporting. Here are the main actions and results of its application: gathering and analysing data strong data gathering techniques were used by Company X, which combined information from a variety of sources, including sales transactions, customer reviews, and supply chain data. To assure the accuracy and dependability of the data, they applied data cleansing processes. It discovered previously undiscovered trends, patterns, and correlations through data research. Data reporting and visualisation: Data visualisation techniques were used by Company X to communicate information in a clear and engaging manner. Key performance indicators (KPIs) were made available in real-time via interactive dashboards and reports, allowing stakeholders to better monitor and analyse company metrics. Decision-making and optimisation: Company X was able to make data-driven decisions with the use of predictive analytics and forecasting methods. It predicted demand, optimised inventory levels, and found possible cost-saving opportunities by examining past data and using machine learning algorithms. As a result, waste was decreased and operating efficiency was increased. Profitability rose: Company X's profitability rose significantly as a result of utilising BI tools and procedures. The team was able to pinpoint and concentrate on high-value clients, refine pricing tactics, and spot chances for upselling and cross-selling. Sales revenue rose as a result, and profit margins also improved.

B. Case study 2: The impact of BI on the growth of SMEs in Country Y

In this case study, we look at how business intelligence has affected the expansion of SMEs in Country Y, an African country. Several SMEs used BI solutions to boost growth and competitiveness thanks to cooperation between the government and regional business support organisations. Here are the main conclusions: Improvement in decision-making SMEs in Country Y made better judgements by using BI tools to collect and analyse data from various sources. These SMEs were in a better position to respond rapidly to market developments, spot new possibilities, and reduce risks because they had access to precise and real-time information. Better consumer insights: SMEs were able to personalise their marketing initiatives, increase customer happiness, and foster customer loyalty by analysing consumer data such as purchase history, preferences, and feedback. Operations were streamlined: SMEs in Country Y improved their operational procedures by implementing BI solutions. By examining data pertaining to production, the supply chain, and resource allocation, they were able to pinpoint bottlenecks, inefficiencies, and places for improvement. Operations were streamlined as a result, and productivity and expenses were decreased. Increased competitiveness: SMEs in Country Y gained an advantage through the use of BI tools and processes. They were able to differentiate their goods or services by analysing competition strategy, identifying market trends, and utilising data insights. Market share grew as a result, and business expansion.

C. Lessons learned and best practises from these case studies

Numerous lessons gained and best practises can be drawn from these case studies, including:

- Align BI implementation with corporate objectives: It is critical for SMEs to coordinate its BI ambitions with overarching corporate goals. Small and medium-sized businesses (SMEs) can make sure that BI solutions provide real value by concentrating on specific objectives like boosting productivity or elevating customer happiness (Vanadzina et al., 2019; Zahoor et al., 2023).
- Invest in data governance and quality: A successful BI implementation depends on accurate and reliable data. To ensure data consistency and integrity, SMEs should invest in data cleansing methods and set up data governance practices (Ashiru et al., 2022).
- Promote a data-driven culture in your organisation: SMEs should encourage a data-driven culture in their businesses. This entails promoting data-driven decision-making among staff members, training them on data analysis software, and fostering a collaborative work atmosphere that appreciates data insights (Zide & Jokonya, 2022).
- Start small and expand gradually: When deploying BI solutions, SMEs should think about starting with a pilot project or a single department. This enables the system to be tested and improved before being implemented throughout the entire organisation (Llave & Llave, 2017).

Gradual scaling guarantees a more seamless deployment and lowers the chance of taxing the company's resources (Llave & Llave, 2017). The effectiveness of SMEs' BI activities must be regularly assessed, and any necessary adjustments must be made. This entails keeping an eye on KPIs, getting user input, and using new technologies or approaches to keep up with the changing business environment. African SMEs may harness the potential of business intelligence to drive growth, better decision-making, and boost their competitiveness in the market by putting these lessons learnt and best practises into real practise.

VI. ADDRESSING THE CHALLENGES AND BARRIERS

In this section we address the challenges and barriers faced by African SMEs in adopting and implementing business intelligence and propose strategies to overcome them.

Business intelligence (BI) implementation in African SMEs has a special set of difficulties. This study examined three significant challenges that these organisations face and speculate on potential solutions. The lack of financing and resources is one of the main obstacles African SMEs encounter when using business intelligence (Mezgebe et al., 2023). Due to its tight financial constraints, many SMEs find it challenging to invest in the infrastructure, technology, and trained labour needed for successful BI deployment (Llave & Llave, 2017). SMEs might look into alternate funding possibilities, such as grants, loans, or partnerships with bigger organisations, to get over this problem. It can also make use of open-source BI tools and cloud-based solutions, which are frequently less expensive than proprietary software (Zide & Jokonya, 2022). Collaboration with academic or research organisations can also give cheaper access to knowledge and resources.

Limited access to technology and infrastructure is a big issue for African SMEs. Hardware, software, and internet connectivity that is dependable are necessary for a successful BI installation (Belhadi et al., 2022). However, a large number of SMEs in Africa are located in areas with poor infrastructure, which makes it challenging to access and make use of the required technologies (Peter et al., 2023). SMEs can take advantage of mobile-based BI solutions that take advantage of the widespread use of smartphones in Africa to address this issue (Onyango & Ondiek, 2021). These programmes can offer data analysis and insights in real-time without requiring substantial infrastructure expenditures. The infrastructure and accessibility of technology in under-served areas can also be improved through cooperation with regional authorities and organisations.

It can be difficult to create a data-driven culture within African SMEs. Many organisations lack the expertise and abilities needed to properly gather, analyse, and understand data. Additionally, there can be a lack of knowledge of the advantages of data-driven decision-making as well as reluctance to change. SMEs should invest in training and development programmes to improve data literacy among staff to get around this problem. This can include gatherings that focus on data analysis, visualisation, and interpretation,

as well as workshops, conferences, and online courses. An organisation's culture of experimentation and curiosity can help develop a data-driven approach. The positive effects of data-driven decision-making are also highlighted, which can assist overcome reluctance and increase employee buy-in. To put it briefly, developing a data-driven culture and addressing resource and financial issues, restricted access to technology, are all necessary for adopting business intelligence in African SMEs. SMEs can get beyond these barriers and enable BI for their organisations by looking into other finance possibilities, utilising mobile-based solutions, and investing in training and development.

VII. RECOMMENDATION FOR FUTURE RESEARCH

With improvements in platforms and applications created for SMEs, business intelligence (BI) is gaining traction throughout Africa. Further study is required to determine how BI adoption affects SME performance, competitiveness, and sustainability. The implementation of BI in African SMEs must also take ethical considerations and best practises into account. In order to develop BI solutions that specifically address the needs and difficulties faced by SMEs in the region, it is crucial to comprehend the cultural, social, and economic settings that are unique to Africa. It is essential for SMEs in Africa to implement BI in order for them to expand and remain competitive in the modern, data-driven business environment. By providing incentives, tax breaks, and grants expressly aimed at SMEs wishing to use BI systems, government assistance and legislation can foster an atmosphere that is conducive to doing so. By providing incentives, tax breaks, and grants expressly aimed at SMEs wishing to use BI systems, government assistance and legislation can foster an atmosphere that is conducive to doing so. Governments can cooperate with organisations and industry professionals to create standardised frameworks and instructions for BI deployment. Investment in digital infrastructure will improve SMEs' access to and effective use of BI tools and platforms, including dependable internet connectivity and inexpensive access to technology.

Moreover, African SMEs can gain a lot from partnerships with technology vendors and industry experts as they move towards adopting BI. Technology suppliers can offer specifically built BI solutions to fit the demands and financial constraints of SMEs, while consultants and industry experts can offer direction and assistance throughout the BI implementation process. Programmes for training and capacity development are crucial for encouraging BI use in African SMEs. Providing thorough training courses on the principles of business intelligence, data analysis methods, and data visualisation can enable SMEs to make data-driven decisions. Partnerships with universities, business schools, or specialised training facilities might be used to deliver these programmes. In a nutshell, encouraging BI use in African SMEs necessitates backing from the government, collaborations with tech companies and industry leaders, and financial investments in skill development. In this way, SMEs in Africa may take advantage of BI's transformative potential to spur development, innovation, and competitive advantage.

VIII. CONCLUSION

This study has examined the significance of encouraging business intelligence (BI) use in African SMEs and has offered suggestions for accomplishing this objective. Let us review the main ideas mentioned, assess how BI might change Africa's economy, and look at potential research directions in the area of BI for African SMEs. We have emphasised the importance of BI adoption in African SMEs throughout this study. We talked about the difficulties SMEs experience in using data successfully and the advantages BI may have for their business. Government assistance, collaborations with IT companies and industry leaders, and training programmes are just a few of the suggestions made, all of which are geared at enabling SMEs to embrace data-driven decision-making and realise their full potential. The potential effects of business intelligence on Africa's transition from a consumption-based economy to one that is industrialised and based on production. The shift in the structure of Africa's economy from a consumption-driven model to a production and industrialised one has the potential to be a game-changer. African SMEs may learn a lot about consumer behaviour, industry trends, and operational inefficiencies by embracing the power of data. Businesses can use this information to produce smart judgements, process improvements, and new goods and services. In the end, BI adoption can boost output, stimulate economic expansion, and establish African SMEs as significant players in the international market.

REFERENCES

- Adam, I. O., Alhassan, M. D., & Afriyie, Y. (2020). Technology Analysis & Strategic Management What drives global B2C E-commerce? An analysis of the effect of ICT access , human resource development and regulatory environment ICT access , human resource development and regulatory. *Technology Analysis & Strategic Management*, 0(0), 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09537325.2020.1714579>
- Adams, K., Attah-boakye, R., Yu, H., Chu, I., & Ishaque, M. (2023). Competence and enterprise of management as drivers of early foreign listing of medium-sized emerging market multinationals (EMNEs) from Africa. *Journal of Business Research*, 158(January), 113660. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2023.113660>
- Agbajor, F. D., & Mewomo, M. C. (2022). Green building research in South Africa: A scoping review and future roadmaps. *Energy and Built Environment*, October. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbenv.2022.11.001>
- Antoniadis, I., Tsiakiris, T., & Tsopogloy, S. (2015). Business Intelligence during times of crisis: Adoption and usage of ERP systems by SMEs. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 175, 299–307. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2015.01.1204>
- Ashiru, F., Adegbite, E., Nakpodia, F., & Koporcic, N. (2022). Relational governance mechanisms as enablers of dynamic capabilities in Nigerian SMEs during the COVID-19 crisis. *Industrial Marketing Management*, 105(August 2021), 18–32. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.indmarman.2022.05.011>
- Belhadi, A., Kamble, S., Fosso Wamba, S., & Queiroz, M. M. (2022). Building supply-chain resilience: an artificial intelligence-based technique and decision-making framework. *International Journal of Production Research*, 60(14), 4487–4507. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00207543.2021.1950935>
- Benzidia, S., & Metz, I. A. E. (2020). The impact of big data analytics and artificial intelligence on green supply chain process integration and hospital environmental performance.
- Bergener, K., Räckers, M., & Stein, A. (2019). The Art of Structuring: Bridging the Gap between Information Systems Research and Practice. In *The Art of Structuring: Bridging the Gap between Information Systems Research and Practice*. Springer International Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-06234-7>
- Brodny, J. (2022). The Level of Digitization of Small , Medium and Large Enterprises in the Central and Eastern European Countries and Its Relationship with Economic Parameters. *Journal of Open Innovation: Technology, Market, and Complexity*, 8(3), 113. <https://doi.org/10.3390/joitmc8030113>
- Cavazza, A., Mas, F. D., & Manzo, M. (2023). Artificial intelligence and new business models in agriculture: a structured literature review and future research agenda. *125(13)*, 436–461. <https://doi.org/10.1108/BFJ-02-2023-0132>
- Dash, R., Rebman, C., & Kar, U. K. (2019). Application of Artificial Intelligence in Automation of Supply Chain Management. *Journal of Strategic Innovation and Sustainability*, 14(3), 43–53. <https://doi.org/10.33423/jsis.v14i3.2105>
- Dumitrascu, O., Dumitrascu, M., & Dobrotă, D. (2020). Performance evaluation for a sustainable supply chain management system in the automotive industry using artificial intelligence. *Processes*, 8(11), 1–20. <https://doi.org/10.3390/pr8111384>
- Gaglio, C., Kraemer-mbula, E., & Lorenz, E. (2022). Technological Forecasting & Social Change The effects of digital transformation on innovation and productivity: Firm-level evidence of South African manufacturing micro and small enterprises. *Technological Forecasting & Social Change*, 182(March), 121785. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2022.121785>

- Gonzalez-tamayo, L. A., Maheshwari, G., & Bonomo-odizzio, A. (2023). digital maturity in Latin America. *Journal of Open Innovation: Technology, Market, and Complexity*, 9(2), 100069. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joitmc.2023.100069>
- Habibzadeh, H., Dinesh, K., Rajabi Shishvan, O., Boggio-Dandry, A., Sharma, G., & Soyata, T. (2020). A Survey of Healthcare Internet of Things (HIoT): A Clinical Perspective. In *IEEE Internet of Things Journal* (Vol. 7, Issue 1, pp. 53–71). IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/JIOT.2019.2946359>
- Hajipour, V., Hekmat, S., & Amini, M. (2023). A value-oriented Artificial Intelligence-as-a-Service business plan using integrated tools and services. *Decision Analytics Journal*, 8(July), 100302. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dajour.2023.100302>
- Helo, P., & Hao, Y. (2022). Artificial intelligence in operations management and supply chain management: an exploratory case study. *Production Planning and Control*, 33(16), 1573–1590. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09537287.2021.1882690>
- Kersten, W., Blecker, T., & Ringle, C. M. (2019). Artificial Intelligence and Digital Transformation in Supply Chain Management: Innovative Approaches for Supply Chains. In *Hamburg International Conference of Logistics*. <http://hdl.handle.net/10419/209196>
- Kubina, M., Koman, G., & Kubinova, I. (2015). Possibility of improving efficiency within business intelligence systems in companies. 26(15), 300–305. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2212-5671\(15\)00856-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2212-5671(15)00856-4)
- Kudama, G., Dangia, M., Wana, H., & Tadese, B. (2021). Artificial Intelligence in Agriculture Will digital solution transform Sub-Saharan African agriculture? *Artificial Intelligence in Agriculture*, 5, 292–300. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aiaa.2021.12.001>
- Li, C. (2022). Data Mining-Based Tracking Method for Multisource Target Data of Heterogeneous Networks. 2022.
- Li, H. (2021). Optimization of the Enterprise Human Resource Management. 2021.
- Lin, H., Lin, J., & Wang, F. (2022). An innovative machine learning model for supply chain management. *Journal of Innovation & Knowledge*, 7((2022) 100276). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jik.2022.100276>
- Llave, M. R., & Llave, M. R. (2017). Business Intelligence and Analytics in Small and Medium-sized Enterprises: A Systematic Literature Review. *Procedia Computer Science*, 121, 194–205. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2017.11.027>
- Manning, L., Brewer, S., Craigon, P. J., Frey, J., Gutierrez, A., Jacobs, N., Kanza, S., Munday, S., Sacks, J., & Pearson, S. (2022). Trends in Food Science & Technology Artificial intelligence and ethics within the food sector: Developing a common language for technology adoption across the supply chain. *Trends in Food Science & Technology*, 125(April 2021), 33–42. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tifs.2022.04.025>
- Mezgebe, T. T., Gebreslassie, M. G., Sibhato, H., & Bahta, S. T. (2023). Intelligent manufacturing eco-system: A post COVID-19 recovery and growth opportunity for manufacturing industry in Sub-Saharan countries. *Scientific African*, 19, e01547. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sciaf.2023.e01547>
- Moyo, M., & Look, M. (2021). Conceptualising a Cloud Business Intelligence Security Evaluation Framework for Small and Medium Enterprises in Small Towns of the Limpopo Province , South Africa.
- Naz, F., Kumar, A., Majumdar, A., & Agrawal, R. (2022). Is artificial intelligence an enabler of supply chain resiliency post COVID-19? An exploratory state-of-the-art review for future research. *Operations Management Research*, 15(1–2), 378–398. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12063-021-00208-w>
- Nikoloski, P. K. (2014). The Role of Information Technology in the Business Sector. 3(12), 303–309.
- Onyango, G., & Ondiek, J. O. (2021). Digitalization and Integration of Sustainable Development Goals (SGDs) in Public Organizations in Kenya.
- Peter, O., Pradhan, A., & Mbohwa, C. (2023). Industry 4 . 0 concepts within the sub – Saharan African SME manufacturing sector. *Procedia Computer Science*, 217, 846–855. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2022.12.281>
- Potgieter, M., Jager, J. W. De, & Heerden, N. H. Van. (2013). An innovative marketing information system: a management tool for South African tour operators. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 99, 733–741. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2013.10.545>
- Richter, L., Lehna, M., Marchand, S., Scholz, C., Dreher, A., Klaiber, S., & Lenk, S. (2022). Artificial Intelligence for Electricity Supply Chain automation. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 163(March), 112459. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2022.112459>
- Sharma, V., Ramirez-asis, E., Ahmad, A. J., Silva-zapata, M., Alvarado-tolentino, J., Kumar, H., & Kraha, D. (2022). On the Internet of Things , Blockchain Technology for Supply Chain Management (IoT). 2022.

Siah, N., Dato, Z., & Yaakob, S. (2016). Assessing the Supply Chain Intelligence Practices of Small Medium Enterprises in Malaysia. *Procedia Economics and Finance*, 35(October 2015), 515–521. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2212-5671\(16\)00064-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2212-5671(16)00064-2)

Toorajipour, R., Sohrabpour, V., Nazarpour, A., Oghazi, P., & Fischl, M. (2021). Artificial intelligence in supply chain management: A systematic literature review. *Journal of Business Research*, 122(September 2020), 502–517. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2020.09.009>

Vanadzina, E., Pinomaa, A., Honkapuro, S., & Mendes, G. (2019). An innovative business Symposium model for rural sub-Saharan Africa electrification Assessing the feasibility of using the heat demand-outdoor temperature function district heat demand forecast. *Energy Procedia*, 159, 364–369. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egypro.2019.01.001>

Zahoor, N., Khan, Z., Meyer, M., & Laker, B. (2023). International entrepreneurial behavior of internationalizing African SMEs – Towards a new research agenda. *Journal of Business Research*, 154(October 2022).

Zide, O., & Jokonya, O. (2022). Factors affecting the adoption of Data Enterprises Management as a Service (DMaaS) in Small and Medium (SMEs). *Procedia Computer Science*, 196(2021), 340–347. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2021.12.022>